

Effects of Resilience and Gratitude on Psychological Well-being among Young Adults

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the effect of resilience and gratitude on psychological well-being among young adults. It is a cross-sectional quantitative type of research in which correlation coefficient and t-test are used to analyze the study variables.

Study was conducted in different colleges and universities of Hyderabad and Jamshoro Cities of Sindh Province during the period of Nov 2021-March 2022.

The sample of the study was young adults of colleges and universities of Hyderabad and Jamshoro with age range of 18-23 years. Sample was drawn by using simple random technique. The total number of participants were 200 (100 males 100 females). Three questionnaires were administered on the participants to collect data. For Resilience 14-items Resilience scale was used For gratitude The Gratitude Scale (GS-6) was used and for psychological well-being Psychological Well-being Scale (PWS) was used.

Results of present study indicated that there is significant positive relationship between resilience and psychological well-being as well as gratitude and psychological well-being. There is significant gender difference found in the scores of all three variables. Females scored high on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being as compared to males.

Current study concluded that there is significant effect of resilience and gratitude on psychological well-being of young adults of Hyderabad and Jamshoro Cities.

Keywords: Gratitude Resilience, Psychological well-being, Young Adults

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INTRODUCTION

Gratitude and “resilience are positive emotions that have a strong influence on the lives of people and their psychological well-being. Some studies support the concept that positive emotions play a vital role in contributing to the psychological and physical well-being of the individual (Tugade et al. 2004). Many researches revealed this fact that well-being improves by participating in intentions like resilience and gratitude. Gratitude is linked with a personal benefit that is not intentionally desired deserve or earned but it is because of the good intentions of another person (Emmons & McCullough 2004). It was always thought that this emotion is very essential for building healthy relationships among people. Gratitude maybe broadly define as an appreciation of what is beneficial and meaningful to one-self. It

shows a usual state of thankfulness and appreciation. Current researches in the field indicated relationship between gratitude and mental health though some researches showed negative relationship as well (Rawat & Gopal 2018). Gratitude is the feeling of gratefulness and delight when one receive any kind of gift even very minute one as described by American Psychological Association. In positive psychology gratitude is the human way of admitting and accepting the good thing of life.

Researches has define gratitude as a positive emotional reaction that we experience on giving or receiving a benefit from someone (Emmons & McCullough 2004). As an emotion gratitude is a two-phase cognitive process: (a) recognizing that something positive has been attained and (b) understanding that the other as an external source is influential in this attainment. The construct of gratitude has been used for implying different concepts such as appreciating the help of others performing rituals achieving optimism and paying attention to positive aspects of life (Sadeghi & Behzadipour 2015). According to Health Education Health Promotion Vol.3 (2015) feeling gratitude in life can bring mental stability happiness physical and psychological health deep-rooted sense of life satisfaction and strong interpersonal relationships (Sadeghi & Behzadipour 2015).

On the other hand resilience is also a very positive quality; resilience helps people have the emotional strength to overcome trauma distress and hardships. Resilience tends to have two distinct meanings: an ability to resist being damaged or deformed by trauma or distressing forces and bouncing back on one's own or retrieving from trauma or destructive forces. The American psychological association defines resilience as the process of adapting well in the adversity trauma threats or even significant sources of stress. Psychologists view resilience as a defense mechanism which helps people to thrive in the face of significant stress. Improving resilience may be an important target for treatment (Davydov et al. 2010).

Carol Ryff (1995) developed a theory to determine six factors that contribute to the development of psychological well-being. It includes positive relationship with others personal mastery autonomy a feeling of purpose and meaning in life and personal growth and development. He also developed psychometric inventory based on these six factors to measure psychological well-being. The emergence and growth of positive psychology has brought about an increase in well-being research which has produced theoretical approaches hedonic and eudemonic (Ryan & Deci 2001). The hedonic view displays the belief of health as an outcome along with an inner state of delight and happiness and focuses on subjective well-being (Pavot & Diener 2008). The eudemonic view posits that well-being includes greater than simply happiness.

A substantial body of research supports the connection between gratitude resilience and psychological well-being (Emmons & McCullough 2003; Kashdan Uswatte & Julian 2006). Researches suggested that gratitude is significantly related to "psychological well-being just like other "positive traits (Park et al. 2004). On the other hand some researches also argued that high level of well-being serve as an antecedent of resilience (Kunt & Malinen 2016). It is seen that people with greater level of gratitude can minimize their depression anxieties and are able to achieve psychological well-being by realizing positive things in their lives (Prabowo 2017). Study conducted on Afghan refugees indicated that resilience and gratitude has significant correlation with psychological well-being (Edriany & Sutatminingsih2020).

SUBJECTS AND METHOD

RESEARCH DESIGN

It was quantitative study with correlational research design. Gratitude and resilience were independent variables and psychological well-being was dependent variable.

PARTICIPANTS

The data were collected from young adults of colleges and Universities. The sample of the present study was collected on 200 participants of the age group of 18 to 23 years. The sample included both male and female. Due to pandemic convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data.

ISNTRUMENTS

Following questionnaires were used to collect the data for the study.

Gratitude Questionnaire (GQ-6)

The gratitude questionnaire was designed to assess individual differences in experiencing gratitude. It is a six items self-report questionnaire design by McCullough Emmons & Tsang (2002). Item 3 and item 6 were having reverse scoring to inhibit response bias. The items were measured on the likert scale ranging from 1 to 7. The GQ-6 has good internal reliability with Alpha between 0.82 and 0.87. It took less than 5 minutes to complete but there was no time limit.

14-items Resilience Scale.

Gail M Wagnild and Heather M Young designed the scale in 1993. It is abbreviated as 14- RS The 14-items resilience scale focuses on the aspects of an individual's psychological resilience patterns of thinking and behaviour that affect their ability to respond positively to setbacks and challenges. It is a self-report measure with 14-items on likert scale ranging from "1" strongly disagree to "7" strongly agree. In addition "4" represent neutral on scale. 14- RS has good psychometric properties with a good level of internal consistency of Cronbach's Alpha= 0.88. In 14-items resilience scale scoring of all items was sequential. If the total of the items can be divided in levels: 82-98 = very high resilience tendencies 64-82= high resilience tendencies 49-63= average 31-48= low resilience tendencies 14-30= very low resilience tendencies.

Psychological well-being Scale

Psychological well-being scale contains 18-items. It was developed by Psychologist Carol R Ryff (1995). It is shortened version of the 42-items psychological well-being scale. The scale is used to measure the different aspects of psychological well-being. These are self-acceptance positive relationship with others purpose in life sense of autonomy personal growth and environmental mastery. All the items are measured on likert scale ranging from 1-7. The scale's internal reliability is Cronbach's Alpha for all facets are 0.52 0.76 0.75 0.52 0.73 and 0.72 respectively. Subscale scores are calculated by adding each item of subscale. When the scores are higher it shows the high level of psychological well-being.

PROCEDURE

Both online and in person methods were used to collect the data. Online sample included 100 participants in which 50 were males and 50 were female and the ratio was same for in person sampling. The data collected from the participants of the ages 18 to 23 and all participants studying in colleges and Universities. The consent was taken from the students before they were given the questionnaires. It was only given to the participants who willingly wanted to be part of the study In the questionnaires the participants were expected to fill the demographic section first which included the information about their gender age socioeconomic status and residential area (Urban-rural).

RESULTS

The following results are obtained by using SPSS version 23. Descriptive statistics has been computed for the demographic information and correlation coefficient and t-test were computed to test the study variables.

Table 1: Demographic Statistics of the participants (n=200)

Demographics	f	%
Gender		
Male	100	50
Female	100	50
Age of participants		
18-20yrs	76	38
21-23yrs	124	62
Participants' Education		
Intermediate	39	19.5
Bachelors	161	80.5
Socio-economic Status		
Upper class	33	16.5
Lower class	14	7
Middle class	153	76.5
Residential Area		
Urban	135	67.5
Rural	65	32.5

Note: f = frequency %= percentage

Table 1 shows frequency and percentages of the participants with respect to gender age socio-economic status and residential area. Male participants (f= 100 %= 50) and female participants (f= 100 % = 50) are equal in number. Participants with age of 21-23 years are higher in number (f = 124 %= 62) as compared to participants with age of 18-20 years (f= 76 %= 38). Participants of Bachelor education are higher in number (f= 161 % = 80.5) as compared to intermediate (f= 39 % = 19.5). Participants of middle class are higher in number (f= 153 % = 76.5) as compared to upper (f= 33 %= 16.5) and lower class (f= 14 % = 7). Participants of urban are higher in number (f= 135 % = 67.5) as compared to rural are (f= 65 %= 32.5).

Hypothesis 1: there will be a positive relationship between resilience and psychological well-being.

Table 2: Correlation between resilience and psychological well-being (n=200)

Variables	M	SD	r	p
Resilience	63.07	12.75	0.557	
0.000				
Psychological well-being	79.38	11.04		

Note: $p \leq 0.01$ $df = 198$

Table 2 shows Pearson correlation between resilience and psychological well-being. Finding indicated that resilience has significant positive correlation with psychological well-being ($r = 0.557$ $p \geq 0.01$).

Hypothesis 2: There will be positive relationship between gratitude and psychological well-being.

Table 3: Correlation between Gratitude and psychological well-being (n=200)

Variables	M	SD	r	p
Gratitude	26.95	5.89	0.468	
0.000				
Psychological well-being	79.38	11.04		

Note: $p \leq 0.01$ $df = 198$

Table 3 indicated Pearson correlation between gratitude and psychological well-being and findings shows significant relationship between gratitude and psychological well-being ($r = 0.468$ $p \leq 0.01$).

Hypothesis 3: There will be significant gender differences in the effects of gratitude and resilience on psychological well-being.

Table 4: Mean Standard Deviation and t-values of male and female on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being

Variables	Male		Female		t	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Resilience	57.61	9.88	68.54	13.00	6.690	.000
Gratitude	25.57	5.54	28.34	5.92	3.412	.001
Psychological Well-being	75.98	8.77	82.78	12.04	4.564	.000

Note: M = Mean SD = Standard Deviation $p =$ level of significance $df = 198$

Table 4 shows mean standard deviation and t values for resilience gratitude and psychological well-being for male and female. Results indicated that there is significant difference on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being scales ($t= 6.690$ 3.4412 and 4.564 respectively). Findings shows that female participants scored higher on resilience ($M= 68.54$ $SD= 13.00$). Gratitude ($M= 28.34$ $SD= 5.92$) and psychological well-being ($M= 12.04$ $SD= 4.564$) as compared to male participants on resilience ($M= 57.62$ $SD= 9.88$) gratitude ($M=25.57$ $SD= 5.54$) and psychological well-being ($M=75.98$ $SD= 8.77$).

Hypothesis 4: There will be significant differences in effects of gratitude and resilience on psychological well-being with respect to residential area.

Table 5: Mean Standard Deviation and t-values of urban and rural on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being.

Variables	Urban		Rural		t	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Resilience .547	63.86	11.30	62.69	13.42	0.640	
Gratitude .174	26.13	5.72	27.34	5.95	1.363	
Psychological .099 Well-being	77.52	9.50	80.27	11.64	1.656	

Note: M= Mean SD= Standard Deviation p= level of significance $df = 198$

Table 5 shows mean standard deviation and t-values for rural and urban on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being. Results indicate that there is no significant difference on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being with $p \geq 0.01$ ($t= 0.640$ 1.363 and 1.656) respectively.

DISCUSSION

The aim of current study was to investigate the effects of resilience and gratitude on psychological well-being in young adults. Gratitude and resilience are positive emotions that have strong influence on the lives of people and psychological well-being. Some studies support the concept that positive emotions play a vital role in contributing to the psychological and physical well-being of the individual (Michele M. Tugade et al. 2004). The sample of 200 participants were taken from different colleges and universities of Hyderabad and Jamshoro cities by using convenient sampling technique. Sample was comprised male=100 and female= 100 with age range of 18-23 years. For first hypothesis correlation was applied between resilience and psychological well-being. Results indicated significant positive correlation between resilience and psychological well-being. Therefore we can conclude that when resilience increases psychological well-being also increases. Sagone & Caroli 2014 also reported same results previously that resilience has significant positive correlation with psychological well-being. For

second hypothesis correlation coefficient was applied to analyses relationship between gratitude and psychological well-being. Results indicated positive correlation between gratitude and psychological well-being. These results are also supported by previous studies that gratitude has positive correlation with psychological well-being (Wood et al. 2010).

For third hypothesis t-test was applied to see the gender differences on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being. Results indicated that female scored higher on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being as compared to males. Previous studies also indicated that female scored higher on gratitude and psychological well-being as compared to males (Ziskis & Bry 1970). For fourth hypothesis t-test was applied to see the difference between urban and rural areas among study variables. Results indicated that there is no difference found on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being in urban and rural areas.

CONCLUSION

Present study concluded that there is significant positive relationship between gratitude and psychological well-being and resilience and psychological well-being Furthermore there is significant gender differences found in the scores of resilience gratitude and psychological well-being where females scored higher on the study variables than males. There is not any difference found in participants belonged to urban and rural areas on resilience gratitude and psychological well-being.

LIMITATION

Present study showed significant results but at the same time there were some limitations. The findings of the study cannot be generalized in other settings like clinical population or elderly people. Sample was collected only from Hyderabad and Jamshoro cities and cannot be generalized in other areas of the Province

IMPLEMENTATION

Gratitude and resilience are very important for the healthy development of individuals. Every individual go through different experiences in which they need to be resilience and learn gratefulness to adjust with them.

1. Colleges and universities should provide strategies and training programs for students to help them learn the negative effects of traumas on their psychological well-being and should provide ways to boost gratitude in them.
2. Seminars and workshops can be organized to give awareness to the individuals regarding practice to increase gratitude and resilience.
3. Students in the academic institutions should also be surveyed to monitor the level of gratitude and resilience in them.
4. There should be seminars held for parents and caregivers on how they can help their child to develop their healthy psychological well-being by boosting attitudes of resilience and gratitude in them.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study highlighted the understanding and evaluated the positive effects of gratitude and resilience on psychological well-being among young adults. Thus the negative effects can also be analyzed in future researches. In addition the sample of current study was young adults other age groups can be used in future studies and see the level of gratitude and resilience in them. The effect of socio-economic status can also be studied in future studies and its effect on gratitude and resilience.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The Authors report no conflict of interest.

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